

To cite this article, Mehmet Aygün, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 4-1, 2023, p. 01 – 18. - 0099-0001-2304-0401.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology

¹St. Clements University, ORCID: 0009-0004-3209-2576

CURRENT SCIENCE

and Driver ...”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

journal with a multi-science peer-review.” (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia”)

””The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.”” (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

””• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.”” (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

Abstract

Today's businesses, in a constantly changing environment, have become organizations that have to act in line with the dominance of the market due to intense competition, their wishes and the expectations and developments of the external environment. Efficiency, which is the success measure of management; While efficiency is a concept that determines the rate of achieving the desired goal in management; first, it means reaching the determined goal by getting results from the management activity. Achieving organizational goals and acting without wasting resources while doing this, achieving maximum output with minimum input constitute the main objectives of businesses. In terms of organizations, labor is the most valuable resource because they control the other two economic resources, capital, and technology. Workforce is the main input of the organization, and all other inputs are processed with human power and transformed into the organization's own power. For this reason, the human resource that provides this power

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

to the organizations is the most valuable resource that can directly affect the efficiency of the organization.

Keywords: *Efficiency, Motivation, Motivation in Businesses*

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

1. Introduction

Instead of the approach based on price competition and reducing factor costs in line with the new efficiency understanding, flexible and information-intensive structures have emerged that foresee the development of product qualities, production organization and management techniques (Yapar, 2005: 23). The important capital of these structures is the human element. Employees: It is a strategic resource in achieving the goals of the organization and providing a sustainable competitive advantage. The employee, which is the most crucial factor in increasing the efficiency of the business, increases efficiency by spending less input and reduces costs (Özgen, Yalçın, 2011: 8).

Motivation is a concept that can only be thought of with the interpretation of behavior (Güney, 2011: 313). Managers who adopt the principle of providing and protecting the motivation of their employees should have a rigorous approach and an attitude that will really motivate them by addressing the expectations of the employees (Kayım, 2018: 34). It is imperative for the manager to interpret the employee's behaviors and to develop models and practices that will motivate them according to the results of this (Güney, 2011: 313).

Management/manager approach and organizational structure, work conditions, individual characteristics of employees, human resources practices, communication and education factors directly affect motivation (Us, 2007: 17). A well-functioning motivation system will allow applications to meet the basic economic needs of the employees, to meet the social needs of the employees, to satisfy the egos of the employees (participation in decisions, etc.), and to improve the skills of the employees (Şimşek et al., 2003: 130).

It is possible to list the motivation tools of managers as follows; eliminating destructive competition, financial and moral incentives, open communication, feedback, participation in decisions and giving responsibility, reasonable hiring practices, focusing on employee strengths, appreciating, and rewarding work, opportunities for promotion, making the job feel important, taking employee complaints into account (Us, 2007: 22-25).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Work performance is the result of capacity to perform, opportunity to perform and willingness to perform. The capacity to do covers skills, knowledge, and experience to the requirements of the job. An individual who does not know how to perform cannot be expected to perform highly. It is not possible to see high performance even if the equipment and needs required for the realization of the work are not provided. The desire to do is whether the employee wants to put forth the effort and effort required for the job (Ivancevich, Matteson, 1990 as cited in Mercanlioglu, 2012: 42). No matter how high the job skill is, if the motivation is low, the performance will be low (Us, 2007: 63).

What one can achieve and what one can overcome are not always on the same level. The term capacity refers to what one can overcome (or potential power); efficiency refers to what one can already accomplish (arising from doing a task). The efficiency of the employee or the work he can achieve depends on his/her willingness to do business with his/her talent, that is, his/her motivation. It is possible to formulate the relationship between these three concepts as follows. Efficiency = Talent X Motivation (Eren, 1979 as cited in Ayhan, 2009: 52).

2. The Concept of Motivation

Motivation comes from the word 'movere,' which means 'to move' in Latin (Adair, 2003: 9; Şimşek et al., 2003: 129). Motivation can be defined as the energy that governs and determines human behavior (Şimşek et al., 2003: 129). In the Turkish Language Association, the word is defined as 'incentive, motivation', while motivation is explained as 'to enable individuals to concentrate their energies in a certain direction by influencing the factors underlying the behavior' (Eroğlu, 2013: 441).

It is possible to list some definitions explaining motivation as follows: (Tınaz, 2013: 5).

- “Persons are acting in accordance with their own desires and wishes in order to achieve a certain purpose”

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

- “It is the process of taking action under the influence of motives and maintaining the behavior until the goal is reached”
- “It is the state of gaining strength to achieve certain purposes”
- “It is a desire to behave. The behavior is sustained as the targeted result carries meaning for the individual”
- “It is the encouragement of individuals to behave in a distinct way with various motives originating from themselves or their environment”

In other words, motivation is the name given to the internal force that ensures the formation, direction, and continuity of the action (Özkalp, 2004: 199). Three elements come to the fore when explaining the concept; the power that forces the individual to engage in a behavior or causes the behavior; the power that enables the behavior to develop in a certain direction and finally the power that ensures the protection and maintenance of the behavior after a behavior emerges (Çalışkan 1985 as cited in Özgener, 2000: 176). In other words, it has three basic characteristics as a motivator, a sustainer of movement and a positive driver (Eren, 2008: 554). The subject of motivation is related to the points of giving information (feedback) about the expectations and needs of people, the goals of people, the behavior of people, and their performance (Koçel, 2007: 483; Eroğlu, 2013: 440).

The motivation for business science is "all of the forces or mechanisms that enable employees to start, continue and fulfill their duties willingly" (Önen and Tüzün, 2005: 22). Since it is a phenomenon that includes values, motives and needs, tensions, and expectations, it is also a behavioral management process in which human behavior is determined, affected, and explained (Eroglu, 2013: 440).

While some definitions of motivation include personal elements such as need and worry, others focus on external factors such as reward and punishment (Ilgar, 2004: 213). Because in addition to the desires and goals that affect the behaviors of the individual and direct the behaviors, there are also some environmental factors such as environmental conditions, personal impressions, social habits, and attitudes (Şimşek et al., 2003: 130). Therefore, motivation, as a source of

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

power that activates the individual, is managed in two dimensions: internal and external (Ersari and Naktiyok, 2012: 83).

Intrinsic motivation is a person's response to intrinsic motives. Curiosity, need to know, desire to be sufficient can be given as examples of intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is the individual's willingness to act and work (Akbaba, 2006: 345). Intrinsic motivation in humans is not the only dimension of motivation, but it is a common and important type. From birth, people are active, enthusiastic, curious, and fun creatures in their healthiest positions, they show that they are ready to learn and explore everywhere, and they do not need an outside incentive to do these (Ryan and Deci, 2000: 56). Intrinsic motivations can be complex, and although money is seen as a short-term incentive, it can also be considered as a sign to be compensated for intrinsic motivations (Andersen, et al., 2016: 74).

External motivation can be expressed with 'external rewards such as avoidance of punishment, competition, reward, good grades' (Kazusa 1999 as cited in Dede and Argün, 2004: 50). There is intrinsic motivation when personal factors come to the fore and extrinsic motivation when environmental factors predominate (Ilgar, 2004: 213). Motivation is accepted as an important phenomenon that directs human relations (Önen, Kanayran, 2015: 44). Learning the source of motivation of the individual reveals the way he focuses on a job/subject, where he receives support while acting towards a goal, his/her decision-making processes and how he is fed (Çam, 2011: 196-197).

In terms of management, motivation and the individual's own efforts and activities make it possible to be directed in line with organizational goals. In other words, it is the willingness of the individual to reveal his/her own existence to meet his/her physiological and psychological needs in achieving organizational goals. By meeting the individual needs of the employee, it can be ensured that the effort required to achieve the goals of the organization is shown at an elevated level. In this way, the organization increases the level of satisfaction of employees as well as efficiency (Robbins, 1996 and De Cenzo and Robbins, 1996 as cited in Önen, Kanayran, 2015: 49-50).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Enabling the individual to reach their goals can also enable the adoption of organizational goals and their concentration for this purpose (Şimşek et al., 2003: 130).

Therefore, the aim of the motivation method is to determine the elements that may create more desire and desire to work in employees and to eliminate them as much as possible and to ensure that they come enthusiastically and work willingly while starting work (Sabuncuoğlu, 1984: 64). In a study conducted in 2010 on this subject, it was determined that when organizations and managers voluntarily acted in good faith, public employees appreciated this and felt obliged to respond with high job performance (Caillier, 2012: 465).

3. Efficiency

Quesnay first used the word efficiency in an article in 1766 (Ceylan, 2009: 63). Francois Quenay defined efficiency as the source of real prosperity in agriculture in his/her work titled 'Historical Perspective of Economic Theories', Adam Smith examined the relationship between labor and division of labor in his/her work called 'Wealth of Nations', proposed efficiency as a concept that the modern world could apply, Karl Marx stated that labor force in manufacturing businesses, discussed the efficiency problems between tools and equipment (Can et al, 2013b: 23). Putting forward the definitions of efficiency will help to understand the concept more clearly.

In a general definition, efficiency is explained as “the relationship between the output produced by a production or service system and the input used to create this output.” Efficiency can also be defined as the relationship between results and the time spent achieving these results (Prokopenko, 1992: 3).

As a term, efficiency is a value calculated by proportioning the output (or the total of outputs) obtained in a certain period, at the end of any production process, to the input (or the total of inputs) used for this purpose in the same period (Demirtaş, Tokat, 2012: 8). In its most general expression, efficiency, which expresses the relationship between the numerous factors (inputs) introduced into the production process and the products (outputs) at the end of this process,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

means to produce by evaluating the resources in the best way, away from extravagance (Yükcü and Atağan, 2009: 5).

Efficiency shows the extent to which available resources are utilized. To increase efficiency, resources should be used more effectively. It is possible to increase efficiency, obtain more products and services from the same sources, or provide the same products and services with less resources. Production refers to how much benefit is created in a system, and efficiency refers to how well the factors of production are used (İleri, 1999: 10).

3.1.Types of Efficiency

Under this heading, the types of efficiency in the literature were examined.

- *Total and Partial Efficiency*

Total Factor Efficiency is defined as the amount of output per unit of inputs, or all factors used in production activities, and this ratio reflects the efficiency gains achieved in the economy. Mostly, this gain is expressed as the efficiency achieved because of the transformation of inputs into outputs with the use of technology (Steindel and Stiroh as cited in Serin and İşcan, 2019: 44-45).

Total factor efficiency is obtained by proportioning the total production to the sum of the inputs involved in production instead of proportioning it to individual inputs. Thus, instead of multiple partial efficiency ratios, a single efficiency ratio is obtained, which shows the efficiency degree of the factors used in production (Abasız, 2006: 23). Total efficiency=Total output/Total input is calculated with the formula (Keskin, 1994: 22).

Partial efficiency is the ratio of output to an input class. For example, labor efficiency and material efficiency or capital efficiency are examples of partial efficiency (Günel, 1995: 2). Since partial efficiency is calculated according to the production factor, it is known as factor efficiency (Ataay, 1988: 7). Partial efficiency is calculated by proportioning the output from

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

production activities to any of the inputs used for production. Partial efficiency eliminates the problems experienced in efficiency measurement since the production factors cannot be expressed in the same unit. In addition, it is measured through partial efficiency, as it allows analysis and detailed examination of the total efficiency that varies or maintains the same level (Ayrıçay, Paksoy, 1999: 43).

- *Physical and Financial Efficiency*

Efficiency types include physical and financial efficiency. If physical units (such as ton meters) play a role in distinguishing the input and output factors that make up the efficiency rate according to the degree of homogeneity, the efficiency rate gives the physical efficiency degree. This concept is a type of efficiency that is mostly used in the field of engineering. In terms of physical quantities in physical efficiency calculation, it is the main purpose to measure how much production is realized by using how much production factor (Abasız, 2006: 6).

Although physical efficiency is seen as the most crude and simple ratio, its meaning and interpretation are considered as indisputable efficiency. In cases where input and output homogeneity are eliminated, it will not be possible to use physical units. In this case, the monetary equivalent of the input and output value units can be calculated. If measurement is to be made with monetary expressions, it is essential to consider input and output price changes (Oğuz, 2007: 14-15). In other words, it can be expressed in monetary or physical units according to the degree of homogeneity of the variables in the efficiency ratio (Çelik, 2000: 15).

- *Average and Marginal Efficiency*

Marginal efficiency is found by proportioning the increase in output in a certain period to the increase in input in the period (Üstün, 1997: 58). The average efficiency is measured by the ratio of the total output of that period to the total input used during the period (Çelik, 2000: 16). With marginal efficiency, the contribution of additional factors of production to production

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

can be determined. Marginal efficiency, which is a type of efficiency that businesses frequently use and attach importance to, provides information to their managers in terms of additional labor purchase, capital, or technology requirements (Uğur, 2003: 52).

When the efficiency measurement is made by considering the totals, it can be calculated as average, and when it is made based on changes, it can be calculated as marginal efficiency. In practice, while average efficiency is used, marginal efficiency is mostly used as an abstract conceptual tool within the scope of theoretical models (in industrial businesses, 1986: 16).

3.2. Employee Efficiency

"Human", which is the most important production factor in the production of economic goods and services in businesses, is the most asset of the business (Sabuncuoğlu, Tokol, 1992: 62). To be able to produce more qualified goods and services than other businesses in the market, to become a leader in terms of technology, to continuously increase sales volume and profitability, to prevent waste by reducing costs, to increase the motivation of employees, to strengthen the image of the business, it is necessary to 'make the workforce efficient.' Organizational goals are achieved only through the efforts of employees and the extent to which an organization is productive and effective depends on the efficiency of its employees (Yumuşak, 2008: 241).

The success of the business is equivalent to increasing the quality of working life and employee efficiency. Although there are managers who create the necessary working environment for efficiency, it is the employees who reach the results using the opportunities in this environment. While the costs of goods and services decrease in organizations with highly productive employees, more output of the desired quality will be achieved with less input (İlgar, 1994: 44). If the expected performance from the employee cannot be obtained, it is not possible to talk about employee efficiency in that business. At the same time, there are numerous factors that affect the efficiency of employees, who are social beings.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

4. Efficiency and Motivation in Businesses

Motivation (motive) is a concept that includes desire, desire, need, impulse, and interests (Cüceloğlu, Human and Behavior, 1998: 229). The motivation process includes three basic elements. The first of these is about what causes behavior, the second is about what directs behavior, and the third is about how this situation is made sustainable (Anık, 2000: 80). The concept of motivation in business can be defined as "all the efforts made to continuously mobilize one or more people towards a certain purpose" (Can et al., 2013a: 301).

Considering the historical development of motivation in businesses, research on the division of labor and motivation as an extension of the Industrial Revolution sought answers to the following question: "What were the reasons why some of the employees in the business worked with great interest and desire, while other employees in the same conditions and with similar abilities worked reluctantly and with low efficiency?". While the rapid development of the industry with the 19th century has enabled production to reach unprecedented dimensions, it has led to the emergence of a sense of uneasiness, dissatisfaction, and unwillingness to work in the working class in the first years (Can et al., 2013a: 303).

In the second half of the 19th century, mechanization and the subsequent automation period led to innovations and changes in the production process. In the process that started with automation, developments such as electronics, cybernetics and computers started the 'information age.' There have been radical changes in the working order of the employees, creating various negative effects on their working habits, traditions, behaviors, and mental structures. However, the leisure time gained through the transition to the automation process has enabled the development of social activities inside or outside the business (Can et al., 2013a: 303-304).

The success of the manager, the work of the work team in line with organizational goals; their knowledge, skills, and power in this direction. Therefore, motivation and performance are two closely related concepts (Koçel, 2007: 483). For this reason, to motivate employees within the framework of business objectives, their desires, wishes and behaviors should be directed in line with organizational goals (Can et al, 2013a: 301).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

The way a person behaves shows his/her motivation. In other words, it reveals the motivation of the person with the desire and effort to do business, to do activities, to get results. It is closely related to the characteristics and expectations of the person and the work done. The work done has different meanings for the person doing the work; the economic value and meaning of the job, the social status and prestige value and meaning of the job, and the psychological value and meaning of the job are some of them. The person brings his/her knowledge, talents and skills, desires, and ambitions to work. Therefore, it is necessary for managers to interpret the behaviors of the personnel and to develop models and practices that will motivate them according to the results of this (Koçel, 2007: 484-485).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

CONCLUSION

Efficiency in organizations is determined by the degree to which members are encouraged and their behavior is directed toward goals. That is, efficiency is the function of incentive, discipline, and other factors in some specific situations. Employee efficiency is associated with his/her talent and motivation, which increases his/her desire to do business. In other words, the same motivation on employees does not lead to the same result due to personality and capacity differences between individuals. Therefore, when motivating, the differences between individuals and capacity should be considered. If it is desired to improve efficiency, it is necessary to motivate the most potentially talented people the most. Because not every person's capacity is the same.

The concept of efficiency is increasingly linked to quality (quality of output, input, and process). A key element is the quality of human resource management and working conditions. The rapid change of products shows that the technical success achieved once will soon become obsolete and need to be renewed. The need to constantly innovate and respond quickly to changes in the market and technology requires a human resource and workforce that offers superior performance. Investing in specialized technology is not an alternative to the ability to manage the workforce, it makes the workforce more important to success. Therefore, ensuring personnel satisfaction and the correct and effective management of human resources are a critical issue in today's business conditions.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

REFERENCES

- Abasız, T. (2006). Growth and Efficiency: The Case of Turkey, Master Thesis. Zonguldak: Zonguldak Karaelmas University Institute of Social Sciences.
- Adair, J. (2003). Effective Motivation: How to Get the Best Out of People. Salih Uyan, Istanbul: Babıali Kültür Publishing
- Akbaba: (2006). Motivation in Education. Journal of Kazım Karabekir Education Faculty, 13:343-361.
- Andersen, N., Murphy, T., Börsch, A. (2016). Nothing for Money. Deloitte Review, 18:71-85.
- Ataay, İ. D. (1988). Factors Affecting Manpower Efficiency in Businesses, Ankara: MESS Turkish Metal Industrialists Union.
- Ayrıçay, Y., Paksoy, H.M. (1999). Business Valuation in terms of its Effect on Efficiency, which is a Lifestyle and a Way of Thinking. Standard: Journal of Technical and Economics, 455:42-48.
- Can, E., Büyükbacı, P., Honey, Y. (2013b). Introduction to Business Science. Istanbul: Beta Publishing.
- Can, E., Büyükbacı, P., Bal, Y., Ertemsir, E. (2013a). Management of Today's Businesses. Istanbul: Beta Publishing.
- Ceylan, A., Ulutürk, Y.H. (2009). Relationships Between Role Ambiguity, Role Conflict, Job Satisfaction and Performance. Doğu University Journal, 7/1:48-58.
- Cüceloğlu, D. (1998). Human and Their Behavior: Basic Concepts of Psychology. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi.
- Çam, Ö. (2011). No stress. Istanbul: Cinius Publications.
- Çelik, N. (two thousand). Input Use in Agriculture and Its Effects on Efficiency, Economic Sectors and Coordination General Directorate, Department of Agriculture Specialization Thesis. Publications

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

of the State Planning Organization.

Publication No:252

Dede, Y., Argun, Z. (2004). Determination of Students' Internal and External Motivations for Mathematics. Cumhuriyet University Journal of Education and Science, 29/134: 49-54.

Demirtaş, U., Tokat, E. (2012). Measurement and Diagnosis in Efficiency Management: An SME Practice. Efficiency Journal, 3:7-38.

Eren, E. (2008). Management and Organization: Contemporary and Global Approaches. Istanbul: Beta Publishing.

Ersarı, G., Naktiyok, A. (2012). The Role of Stress Management Techniques in Employee's Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation. Atatürk University Journal of Social Sciences Institute, 16/1: 81-101.

Güney: (2011). Organizational behavior. Ankara: Nobel Publishing.

İleri, H. (1999). Efficiency, Concepts Related to Efficiency and Importance of Efficiency in Terms

of Businesses. Selçuk University Journal of Vocational School of Social Sciences, 1/2:9-24.

Ilgar, Ş. (2004). Motivational Activities and Teacher. Hasan Ali Yücel Journal of the Faculty of Education, 2:211-222.

Kayım, Nurdan. (2018). Motivation in the Context of Herzberg's Double Factor Theory: The Devil Wears a Brand Film. International Journal of Community and Cultural Studies, 1:31-45.

Keskin, U. (1994). Efficiency Analysis and Its Application in a Business, Master Thesis. Istanbul University Institute of Science and Technology.

Koçel, T. (2007). Business Management. Istanbul: Arıkan Publishing.

Mercanlioğlu, Ç. (2012). The Relationship Between Performance Management and Employee Motivation in Organizations. Journal of Organization and Management Sciences, 4/1:42-52.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

- Öğuz, F. (2007). Work Measurement Technique for Increasing Efficiency in Businesses and an Application, Master Thesis. Ankara University Institute of Social Sciences, Ankara.
- Önen: M., Kanayran, H. G. (2015). Leadership and Motivation: A Theoretical Evaluation. Journal of Individual and Society, 5/10: 43-63.
- Özgen H., Yalçın, A. (2011). Human Resource Management: A Strategic Approach. Adana: Nobel Bookstore.
- Prokopenko, J. (1992). Efficiency Management: A Practical Handbook.
- Ryan, Richard M., Deci, Edward L. (two thousand). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations: Classic Definitions and New Directions. Contemporary Educational Psychology, 25, 54-67.
- Sabuncuoğlu, Z. (1984). Psychology of work. Bursa: Uludag University Press.
- Seminar Notes on Efficiency Measurement and Analysis in Industrial Businesses. (1986), National Efficiency Center Industry Branch. Ankara: MPM Publications.
- Serin, D., İşcan, E. (2019). The Effect of Information and Communication Technologies on Efficiency: The Case of Turkey. Efficiency Journal, 3:41-55.
- Şimşek, M.Ş., Akgemci, T. Çelik, A. (2003). Introduction to Behavioral Sciences and Behavior in Organizations. Konya: Adım Publishing.
- Tınaz, P. (2013). Case Studies from Working Life. Istanbul: Beta Publications.
- Uğur, A. (2003). Efficiency in Business Lecture Notes. Sakarya: Sakarya Kitabevi Publications.
- Us, A. T. (2007). Motivation in Businesses, Istanbul: Economic Business and Business Ethics Association Publication.
- Üstün, R. (1997). How to Increase the Efficiency of the Labor Force. Anadolu University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Journal, 13/1:55-70.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Yapar, T. (2005). The Effect of Motivation on Work Efficiency, Master Thesis. Istanbul University Social Sciences Institute

Yumuşak: (2008). A Field Study on the Investigation of Factors Affecting Employee Efficiency. Journal of the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences of

Süleyman Demirel University, 13/3: 241-251.

Yükçü: Atağan, G. (2009). Confusion Created by the Concepts of Efficiency, Effectiveness and Efficiency. Atatürk University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences, 23/4:1-13.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE